

Preserving Cultural Heritage: Analysis of the Endangered Mashru Weaving Handloom Tradition in India

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Abstract:

India is renowned for its diverse range of traditional crafts, reflecting the country's rich cultural heritage. The artistic talent and cultural diversity of its regions are reflected in the exquisite fabrics, vivid pottery, sophisticated metalwork, and jewellery that are handcrafted using old skills that have been passed down through centuries. However, numerous such crafts and art forms are facing significant decline, rendering them endangered and on the verge of extinction. The study explores the craft of "Mashru" weaving, an old textile technique that originated in Persia and has been diligently practiced in India for numerous centuries. This old technique utilizes a unique weaving approach in which cotton threads are used to create the inside surface, while silk yarns are employed to produce a glossy outside surface. The traditional Mashru weaving industry, however, has been significantly impacted by the advent of broad industrialization and the extensive manufacture of textiles using machines. This has resulted in a decrease in the number of artists practicing this craft and a potential risk of losing this valuable cultural heritage.

The primary objective of this study is understand the complex process of Mashru weaving and to conduct a detailed investigation of the operational dynamics inside a Mashru craft cluster situated in Patan, Gujarat. The research methodology entails conducting a comprehensive physical survey to document and assess the current challenges faced by Mashru weavers. This assessment covers various aspects, including the accessibility of raw materials, market demand, economic viability, and the socio-cultural elements that impact the activity. The research highlights the weavers' resilience in facing problems and their ability to adapt by using creative design strategies and collaborating with others to grow their consumer base.

Keywords: *Artisan Challenges, Cultural Preservation, Mashru Weaving, Patan Craft Cluster, Textile Heritage*

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1. Introduction

'Mashru' is adapted from an Urdu word meaning 'Permitted.' The craft of Mashru is a product of direct influence through Islamic culture in Indian textiles. As per Islamic beliefs, Silk must not touch the skin. However, Silk was considered a luxurious material worn by the royals and prominent members of society. To fulfil the need to wear Silk, the process of Mashru was introduced, which had a unique weaving style having the outer layer weaved of silk threads and the inner of cotton [1, 2].

Figure 1 - Finished mashru cloth

Mashru is a simple Indian fabric with a shiny, satin finish. It is woven in a combination of linear waves and similar patterns. This type of cloth is speciated for clients with strong religious sentiments and beliefs.

The fabric has also developed to accustom the contemporary styles where the Silk has also been replaced with satin. The material is unique as it has a silk warp with a cotton weft, and traditional designs use a tie and dyed yarn, generating a vibrant striped pattern on the fabric. Mashru is mainly developed using bright colors, so the spectrum of colors used includes mainly shades of red, green, and yellow. Due to the satin weave technique, threads of flowing Silk literally float on the cotton weft, like a personification of Silk lying on a cotton bed. The fabric is a taste to the eye of the viewer, who embarks on the vibrant Silk on the exterior while the user stays in the comfort of cotton, figure 1 [3, 4].

As the process of weaving Mashru is tedious and expensive, it has seen a decline in demand since industrialization. While not as famous as Patola nor unique to Patan, is Mashru weaving also a craft worth deserving? Some Kutchi communities use the fabric to stitch garments for their dowry. The cloth was also exported to Turkey and the Middle East. Once made throughout India, the weaving of Mashru has become limited only to a few places. There is now an additional area known as the “Tankwada ni Pol”, where there is an effort to revive the craft. There is a similar craft in Andhra Pradesh known as Kunti is produced. The present use of Mashru is primarily seen in home furnishing and garments. The paper further explores the issues faced by the craftspeople, which is leading to a decline in the practice of the craft.

2. Methodology of study

The methodology of the study is based on a physical survey and documentation conducted at Patan, Gujarat. Stage one of the research is focused on documenting the process of the craft, using a participatory observation tool and one-to-one unstructured interviews with the craftspeople. The inquiry is based on the present condition of the craft, the marketing channels, and the future survival of the craft. The second phase of the study entailed a comprehensive examination to determine the challenges encountered by the craft cluster in maintaining and perpetuating their traditional techniques. The data was collected through one to one participatory interviews, employing an unstructured questionnaire which allowed for deep discussions and further record narrative type responses of the crafts people. The weaver's cluster in Patan has been identified for the study as it is the only functional and largest surviving cluster in the region.

3. Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is based on 8 parameters identified from the relevant literature and other secondary sources. It is further refined through the interactions and inputs of concerned officials and other stakeholders. The parameters and indicators of the study is further discussed in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters and Indicators of the study

Sl. No	Parameters	Indicators
1	Craft Techniques and Practices	Traditional methods and tools used. Changes or adaptations over time. Challenges in preserving original techniques.
2	Market Dynamics	Current demand for their products. Primary markets and customer demographics. Competition from industrial or machine-made products.
3	Economic Viability	Cost of raw materials and production. Profit margins and pricing challenges. Availability of financial support or subsidies.
4	Social and Cultural Factors	Role of the craft in local traditions and identity. Community support and involvement. Impact of generational shifts and younger artisans' interest.
5	Skill development and Training	Opportunities for formal or informal training. Challenges in attracting workforce.
6	Infrastructure and Resources	Availability of raw materials. Access to tools, equipment, and workspace. Role of government policies and initiatives.
7	Sustainability and Innovation	Efforts to integrate sustainable practices. Potential for modern innovations
8	External Support and Collaborations	Collaboration with NGOs, Government and Private organizations. Participation in exhibitions, fairs, or global markets. Usage of e-commerce platforms.

4. Mashru Craft Cluster of Patan

The cluster selected for the study of Mashru craft is the only living cluster in Patan. The cluster has six craftspeople who operate under one trader, who is responsible for significant orders and marketing of the cloth. Few craftspeople work in mixed mode, where they are tied with the traders and work individually on pre-ordered demands from traders of Surat, Ahmedabad, and Palanpur. Although the cluster is identified by the Ministry of Textiles, due to its small coverage, they have not been allotted the GI registration, such as the Patan Patola, which creates a problem in targeted market publicity and production.

4.1 Status of Craft Cluster

The mashru cluster in Patan is dominated by the Wankar communities, who are also known to be the creators of this craft form. They are located at Koshwani Pol, situated near the Koteswar Mahadev temple. The cluster comprises of 8 craftspeople, including three master craftsmen, three craftspeople, and two apprentices.

There are approximately six families working in the Mashru Craft. Of the 6 families working only 1 family has a woman working in this field, figure 2 shows some of the craftsmen working in the pol. Though this had been a hereditary occupation, none of their current generations is employed in this field.

Figure 2 - Craftspeople in the Cluster

3.1.1 Description of Craft Practices

In the Mashru craft cluster at Patan, the cluster has one local dealer responsible for the cluster's trades. The craftspeople are waged employees; they are paid monthly/ amount of work produced based on salaries. These craftspeople also work and sell on individual bases when there are orders from other dealers who come to them. Mostly these orders are from dealers from Ahmedabad and Palanpur, figures 3&4 shows the organisation of the craft cluster and the flow of work in the cluster.

Figure 1 - Work flow chart of the cluster

Figure 4 - Cluster Organisation

The craft of Mashru has declined slowly with time, the most prominent use of this weave is by Kutchi women who stitch garments for their dowry. There are few clusters that are still surviving working with this traditional craft. The revival project taking place at Tankwada Ni Pol, is based on the traditional designs and quality. Today, the craft has been majorly replaced with the industry-manufactured cloth. Figure 5&6 show the looms installed at the artisan's residence.

3.2 Issues and Challenges faced by the Mashru Weavers

Figure 5 - Artisan working at the handloom

Mashru is still produced using conventional methods indulging high and skilled manpower using indigenous technology. The survey and interviews presented several shortcomings faced by the artisans which has led to the decline of the craft. The practise of mashru is dwindling due to several reasons, including lack of demand and awareness among people, insufficient market connectedness, a lack of variation in designs, laborious manufacturing process not supported by technological advancement, bad socio-economic conditions of weavers, etc. To understand these in detail it is important to understand the ecosystem of the craft which includes its manufacturing, raw material used, manpower required, design, marketing, performance, etc.

5. Manufacturing Process

The process of weaving Mashru is organised with a series of stages developed by the professional craftsmen. The work is distributed across a series of artisans from the initiation to final product development. Taani preparation, Rangai, mending of damaged yarns, Pavat, Rach preparation, Saandhani, Weaving, and Kundi are the primary production procedures. Artisans who are involved in the preparation of the Mashru are listed below:

- i. Tania wala or Tani wala – There are the artisans who develop the first wrap. Locally the process is called Tani preparation, performed by Tani wala (warper) [4].
- ii. Panar or Pavaat – There are the artisans involved in starching the silk yarn / viscose rayon threads to make it taut and shiny.
- iii. Rangrez- These are the local dyers who colour the yarn. This process is called Rangai in local language.
- iv. Rach (Shaft) maker - Shaft (Rach) preparation comprises inserting threads into the loom's heddle to display the design. They are the one who prepare the basic outline of the design called naksha in local language. The rach maker drew the pattern's naksha and installed them on the loom.
- v. Rajbhara – These are the artisans involved in the preparation of the design on the heddle for the weavers [5]. The task is completed by threading warp yarn through the heddles of different shafts in line with the interlacing order, leaving the ends hanging over.
- vi. Weavers- These are the artisans involved with weaving, locally known as Bunai.
- vii. Saandhani wala or Sandhni wala- These are the artisans who joins the new yarns with tail end of previous one.
- viii. Kundi wala- These are the artisan who calendars the fabric, which is known as Kundi in local language. After the weaving is complete, the fabric is cleaned in cold water, folded, and battered with wooden hammers for 10 minutes on the wrong side by two Kundi walas. This calendaring permits all warp threads to appear uniformly on the right side of the fabric.

The figure 6 shows the step wise manufacturing process of piece dyed and yarn dyed mashru.

Traditionally, the warp (the vertical threads) of a Mashru fabric is woven with silk yarn, while the weft (the horizontal threads) is woven with cotton [6]. The manufacturing process has evolved over the prior to accommodate the changing market trends. In the past few decades, artists have created a commercial category of fabric based on rayon, a semi-synthetic manmade fibre material.

The complicated production mechanism of mashru has confined its practice to a small number of households in Patan. Complexity of the pit-based handloom and the antiquated machinery used to weave the fabric has hindered modernisation of the craft. Hence this practice is confined to a specific region with only handful trained people working with it. Figure 7 shows the broad manufacturing steps of the Mashru craft.

Figure 2 - Manufacturing process of Piece Dyed Mashru and Yarn Dyed Mashru

Figure 3 - Manufacturing process of Mashru [7]

3.1 Raw Material

The Mashru is made in Patan, traditionally it is a mixed fabric of Silk and cotton. In recent years the opulent silk warp of the original fabric has been replaced with rayon in Patan and cotton in the Kutch-Bhuj region in order to make the cloth more accessible and increase its overall output [8].

Alternatively, staple cotton, mercerized cotton, and staple rayon are used as wrap for Mashru fabric. While Mulberry silk and Tasar are considered specialty yarns, Rayon mashru falls within the commercial category. This Patan rayon mashru fabric is usually 36 inches wide and is made in the handloom using 120s to 150s rayon in the wrap and 30s cotton in the weft [2]. The products majorly used by consumers are blouses, skirts, and shawls. The manufacturing process is labor- and time-intensive, which impedes the capital flow for an extended period. The artisans work on a per-order basis since they have little funds to invest in raw materials. This is one of the most significant obstacles to scaling the craft.

4 Infrastructure

The traditional production mechanism of mashru weaving has not been altered since its first conception. The looms that the craftspeople in Patan cluster use are very old and have a simple mechanism that requires coordination between the feet and hands. This loom is called a "pitloom" because it is placed in a pit and is controlled by foot pedals [9]. Figure 8 show an artisan working in the pit loom.

Figure 4 - Artisan working in the pit loom

There are craftspeople in Patan cluster who are practicing the craft of mashru weaving in their own houses. There is a lack of central working facility, warehouses, skill development centre and commercial establishments at the local level. But most of the artisans are now considered as laborers, taking simple orders from the *vyapari* (dealer or middle man) as their knowledge about marketing and distribution is very limited. This has necessitated the establishment of cluster based infrastructure consisting of a central manufacturing plant, training centres, storage facilities, and exhibition spaces to sustain the craft's eco-system.

5 Human Resources

The mashru weavers in Patan cluster are mostly the older generation, whereas the younger generation is slowly drifting away from the craft of weaving to more lucrative jobs away from the cluster. The ardent practitioners of this craft are in their sixties and labour nearly eight hours per day. As the craft produces low returns for the craftsmen, the current generation is slowly migrating to the cities in search of more stable, well-paying employment [10]. The majority of weavers are employed by a local merchant who sells the fabric and pays a daily wage. Therefore, wages are poor and the number of artisans decreases from generation to generation. There is a scarcity of rach makers who can manage intricate patterns and diverse weaving techniques, which is cause for concern in craft expansion [4]

This has generated a demand for trained artisans with traditional and comprehensive understanding of the manufacturing process and other professionals understanding the dynamics of market, all working cohesively under one umbrella.

6. Marketing and Promotion

The market demand of the mashru is limited due to several reasons. Most of the artisans work for the middle man on order basis and are not involved in direct marketing of their product. The artisans lack training in the two main business verticals, namely marketing and distribution of the product. The handloom is facing a setback due to its lack in promotion. In one practise, artisans approach a variety of government-sponsored exhibitions and markets. These exhibitions are held throughout the nation and throughout the year. However, these exhibitions are dominated by master weavers and recognised crafts. Even today the weavers are dependent on traditional marketing channels such as exhibit sales, local fairs, emporium, etc.

The survey also revealed that cluster representatives rarely provide feedback to real cluster actors, even after returning from state-funded international trips. Networking is another major challenge faced by these weavers. Local markets or shops that sell the crafts people's items directly are scarce or non-existent. There is no formal space allocated for exhibition in the local area for artisans. Artisans are not trained to align their productions according to the sales data. Even cluster actors are unaware of the specifics of minor export orders, including the international and domestic sale, acceptance/rejection, required documentation, and procedures. Therefore, the cluster has not generated any export data.

Handloom is far underperforming in promotion and advertising of its product when compared to the textile industry. In most instances, promotion is limited to exhibitions and fairs with its small representation in the same. As a result, the client only buys when it's accessible and switches to a competitor product when it's not.

7. Design & Innovation

The cluster's design capabilities have not kept up with the times. The craft of conventional design has dwindled as the best designers have passed away, leaving those who remain with limited capabilities and resources to improve. There are no modern-day designers working in the cluster, and while some state agencies have recruited them in the past, the benefits of their work have not been passed on to the cluster in any form that is sustainable. They've only ever worked as one-time interventions in a static mode. The weaver is completely cut off from fashion forecasting difficulties.

As a result, most weavers are impacted by design and product development challenges. The challenge in this area is to start by identifying and analysing the available skills and resources, then move on to skill upgradation,

improving the quality of the mashru fabric, design development by contemporizing the existing design vocabulary, product diversification, and experimentation to discover new and innovative possibilities.

Several mashru weavers have also branched out to weave cotton stripes and checks, which are in more demand and easier and cheaper to produce. As a result of testing with various widths, weights, and materials, other applications for the fabric were discovered, taking it beyond a simple yardage fabric and resulting in a far more diverse product line.

8. *Performance/ability of the cluster*

The skill that persists within this craft cluster is highly commendable. Most of them possess a lot of government and non-government accreditations acknowledging their work. Hence there is no question raised in the sheer competency of this cluster. However, the crafts people lack quality control and market feedback which is an essential parameter to maintain and develop a consumer market. Quality of the products are mostly compromised and because most craftsmen are related to each other they lack competition between each other. Moreover, they are financially weak and are dependent on the middleman or a trader for work. The product produced by the cluster is of poor quality as the cost provided to the artisans is not sufficient to procure good raw material.

9. *Institutional Linkages*

Design institutes and designers these days wish to collaborate with these craftsmen in many of their projects. But the craftsmen are so comfortable in their own space and constitution that they reject moving to another space or being disturbed in their regular style of working. A link to this stratum of innovators shall open a wide avenue for these artisans in their field. Within the cluster, information is difficult to come by. For example, the weaver is unaware of the visits of designers to the cluster, even those supported by government organisations, resulting in a limited interface.

10. *Conclusion*

Mashru weaving is a traditional technique struggling to make its survive in the contemporary world. The artisans in association with the craft are facing issues with the survival in the fast-growing market, where they are highly challenged by the machine production of such cloth material. The artisans are slowly moving towards different opportunities, as the products sold by them are majorly outdated or not in sync with contemporary fashion. There is a need for Markets that would bring in new information and design ideas, as well as keep the sector up-to-date on a global scale. There is a need to formulate a mechanism to document and analyse the feedback of customers on design. The artisans should be trained by the experts to document and analyse various consumer behaviour data and sales data. They should also be empowered with various tools to understand the consumer behaviour and update their product design to suit the requirement. Small and customised lots are becoming increasingly popular in the industry. As a result, weavers must be taught to create a customised product, which can also serve as a core skill for handloom products.

Reserving a spot in government-sponsored exhibitions held across India are an effective medium to gain exposure for artisans at domestic and international level. New marketing methods, such as e-commerce, need to be integrated alongside more conventional methods for extending the presence of the craft. There is a need to organise and modernise this weaving craft by eliminating the middle layer and empowering artisans, who are the primary stakeholders. Researching and adopting the successful western model is essential for the Indian market, where discerning consumers care more about the quality and value of handlooms than merely demonstrating their altruism.

For handloom goods to make an indelible impression on consumers, the industry needs constant promotion via print and online media. This can be achieved through collaborations with E-commerce platforms. The integration of technology within the operational frameworks of Indian craftspeople is crucial for improving their visibility in the market and ensuring long-term sustainability. Thus training programs that emphasise usage of digital tools should be introduced by the Government for craftspeople. This will help the craftspeople to effectively communicate the cultural heritage and unique craftsmanship that characterise their products. It is also suggested to create an integrated online marketplace to improve craft visibility within competitive markets and also expands the customer base by providing government backed authenticity. An online presence also lets craftsmen monitor

consumer behaviour and market trends, which helps them evaluate product demand. This information can be used to diversify and innovate products, keeping them relevant in modern markets while preserving old methods.

There is a need to identify the market and create suitable products for the survival of prevailing techniques and traditions. The vocal for local initiative may be taken as a catalyst to extend the reach of the Mashru handloom.

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